

Letter to the Editor

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INUSphere®-Concept Can Eliminate Immunocomplexes and Micro Plastics - Letter to the Editor

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Dear Editor,

Since I had introduced and established the therapeutic plasma exchange in 1979, later the immunoabsorption and other methods in the Nephrology Department of the University Clinic of Saarland, Homburg, Germany, I am very interested in the Therapeutic Apheresis (TA). I presented on various national and international congresses over different years the own results and published them and wrote reviews of these blood purification methods [1]. I was always surprised about the results after some TA treatments in combination with the immunosuppressive or other necessary drug therapy in patients.

Some months ago, I met an old friend Richard Straube MD, who is since several years the chief physician of the clinic in Cham, Bavaria, Germany. I want to introduce his new INUSphere®-concept,

which based on a new therapy concept of the double membrane filtration method with the second hollow fiber membrane TKM58 which has Richard Straube adapted to a new hardware system some years ago [2-5]. This INUSphere®-concept can eliminate immunocomplexes, inflammatory mediators, and other toxic substances, and especially micro plastics, from the blood. The patients with severe diseases can be stabilized and improved under this treatment, after only some treatments. The INUSphere®-concept is more successful than the therapeutic plasma exchange method. Especially, the elimination of micro plastics from blood is important for today and in future time. Richard Straube can present a manuscript with graphics of eliminated micro plastics, which were found in the blood of treated patients and analyzed from the TKM Sub Health

Laboratory GmbH, INUS Medical Center, Cham, Bavaria, Germany.

The INUSphere®-concept as a further developed double filtration plasmapheresis system with the second hollow fiber TKM58, consists of polymer, is used successfully over several years in different diseases, such as environmental-, autoimmune-, inflammatory-, dermatological-, cancer-, long COVID diseases and others [6]. The modified double membrane filtration system is used in Germany, in different European countries and in some countries of Asia. The advantages are a high effectivity and a low rate of side effects. Only some treatments are necessary to stabilize or improve the patients. INUSphere® is a whole new medical concept which is superior to other TA methods and has more advantages such as effectivity, low side effects, to improve different severe diseases, etc. This new double filtration plasmapheresis system with immunosuppressive or other necessary drug therapy is very successful in the treatment of severe diseases. Especially, the elimination of micro plastics from the blood of patients with the INUSphere® is high and very effective. Therefore, the INUSphere® can be recommended as treatment for diseases, which are untreatable with conservative therapy. The INUSphere®-concept is carried out in specialized hospitals.

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